

Building visual attention maps through ergodic saccadic trajectories

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Abstract Intelligent systems rely on active vision to dynamically interact with their environments, using mechanisms such as selective visual attention to prioritise relevant information and enable efficient perception [1]. Inspired by the human visual system, characterised by foveated explorative vision to fixate targets, D’Angelo et al. [2] replicate fixational and saccadic eye movements to detect and shift the gaze towards salient features in dynamic scenes. Event-based cameras, such as Dynamic Vision Sensors (DVS), capture asynchronous scene changes with low latency and low power consumption. Building on this foundation, we extend a prior learning-free framework [2] that combines a Spiking Convolutional Neural Network (sCNN) with a DVS for real-time attention-guided saccades through object motion sensitivity. Considering that the field of view (FoV) of event-based cameras is limited relative to the full scene, and that dynamic environments require revisiting regions to capture changes, we formulate the construction of a comprehensive visual attention map as an *ergodic exploration* problem. Ergodic exploration offers a principled framework that ensures salient regions, identified using [2], are revisited in proportion to their importance, while also guaranteeing full scene coverage as exploration time increases.

Methods The human retina features receptive fields that shrink non-linearly toward the fovea, enabling high-resolution central vision and coarse-grained peripheral context. This structure underpins foveation, a mechanism whereby salient stimuli in peripheral vision guide the fovea to sequentially inspect regions of interest (ROIs). This dynamic allocation of visual resources balances broad-scene monitoring with fine-detail analysis, supporting rapid and accurate recognition in cluttered environments. D’Angelo et al. [2] developed an event-based bio-inspired learning-free selective attention system that integrates a Spiking Convolutional Neural Network (sCNN) with a Dynamic Vision Sensor (DVS). This architecture mimics fixational eye movements and performs saccadic shifts toward motion-based ROIs, achieving a latency of 0.124s from collecting events to executing foveation. The approach achieved 82.2% mean IoU and 96% SSIM on EVIMO, with salient object detection accuracies exceeding 88% in both structured and low-light conditions (LLE-VOS). To enhance scene exploration and mitigate attention biases, we

employ ergodic control to generate trajectories for saccadic movements. Given a target spatial distribution, such as a saliency map, the ergodic controller produces trajectories that allocate time to each region proportionally to its saliency. This approach ensures that, over time, the explored regions collectively converge to the target saliency distribution, providing comprehensive visual coverage and increasing the robustness of perception in dynamic environments.

Preliminary Results As a preliminary experiment, we collected events over a 124 ms window and generated a saliency map of a scene containing objects placed on a shelf. We then computed the saccadic ergodic exploration trajectory using a transient diffusion-based ergodic controller [3], as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: **Ergodic Saccades:** a) The saliency map collected over approximately 124 ms, b) Ergodic trajectories exploring the saliency map.

References

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